

Comparative Impact of Medical Nutrition Therapy versus Standard Nutrition Therapy on Severe Thinness in Children Aged 5 to 10 Years

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Received: 05-04-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 13-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This randomized controlled trial assessed the efficacy of Medical Nutrition Therapy (MNT) versus Standard Nutrition Therapy (SNT) in treating severe thinness among children aged 5 to 10 years. Over six months, 120 participants received either personalized nutritional plans (MNT group) or standard dietary guidelines and supplements (SNT group). Results indicated that MNT led to significantly better outcomes in terms of BMI percentile increase, height and weight gains, and improvements in serum iron and vitamin levels. The MNT group also experienced fewer health complications. These findings suggest that individualized nutritional interventions are crucial in managing severe thinness in children, offering insights into optimizing pediatric nutritional strategies.

Keywords: Medical Nutrition Therapy, Standard Nutrition Therapy, Severe Thinness, Pediatric Nutrition.

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Introduction

The alarming prevalence of severe thinness among children globally, particularly in those aged 5 to 10 years, necessitates effective interventions to combat malnutrition and ensure optimal growth and development during crucial formative years [1]. Severe thinness in children is not only a marker of undernutrition but also a predictor of poor health outcomes, including increased susceptibility to infections, delayed cognitive development, and higher mortality rates. Addressing this public health issue requires targeted nutritional interventions tailored to the needs of this vulnerable population [2,3].

Medical Nutrition Therapy (MNT) and Standard Nutrition Therapy (SNT) are two primary approaches employed to address severe thinness in children [4]. While SNT provides general dietary guidelines and supplements to meet daily nutritional requirements, MNT offers a more tailored therapeutic approach, considering individual medical conditions and nutritional deficiencies. This study aims to assess and compare the efficacy of MNT versus SNT in improving nutritional status and overall health in children aged 5 to 10 years suffering from severe thinness [5,6].

By conducting a structured comparison between these two nutritional therapies, this study seeks to provide empirical data on their relative

effectiveness [7]. The findings are expected to guide healthcare professionals in selecting the most appropriate therapy based on clinical outcomes, thereby improving the management strategies for child malnutrition and contributing to the broader goals of pediatric health promotion and disease prevention [8,9].

The primary aim of this study is to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of Medical Nutrition Therapy (MNT) versus Standard Nutrition Therapy (SNT) in improving the nutritional status and overall health outcomes of children aged 5 to 10 years diagnosed with severe thinness. This research seeks to identify which therapeutic approach is more beneficial in correcting nutritional deficiencies and enhancing growth parameters in this vulnerable age group. By systematically analyzing the impacts of these two distinct nutrition therapies, the study intends to provide actionable insights that can inform clinical practices and policy decisions regarding nutritional interventions for malnourished children.

Methodology

Study Design and Period: This study employs a randomized controlled trial (RCT) design to assess the effectiveness of Medical Nutrition Therapy (MNT) versus Standard Nutrition Therapy (SNT) in children with severe thinness. The research will

be conducted over six months, from November 2016 to April 2017.

Participants: The study will include a sample of 120 children aged 5 to 10 years diagnosed with severe thinness, defined as a body mass index (BMI) below the 5th percentile for their age and sex according to the World Health Organization growth charts. Participants will be recruited from pediatric outpatient clinics and community health centers.

Randomization and Grouping

Participants will be randomly assigned to one of two groups:

1. Medical Nutrition Therapy Group (MNT Group): 60 children will receive individualized dietary plans based on their specific nutritional deficiencies and health needs.

2. Standard Nutrition Therapy Group (SNT Group): 60 children will receive general dietary recommendations and nutritional supplements based on standard pediatric guidelines.

Intervention

- **MNT Group:** Each child in the MNT group will undergo a thorough initial assessment by a registered dietitian, who will design a personalized nutrition plan that addresses specific deficiencies and medical conditions. Follow-up assessments and adjustments to the dietary plan will occur monthly.
- **SNT Group:** Children in the SNT group will receive a set of standardized nutrition guidelines and supplements intended to meet the average nutritional needs of children their age.

Data Collection: Baseline data, including demographic information, medical history, dietary habits, and detailed anthropometric measurements (height, weight, BMI), will be collected at the start. Follow-up data will be collected at the end of the study period to assess changes in nutritional status, growth parameters, and health outcomes.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be analyzed using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize the data. Comparative analysis between the two groups will be performed using paired t-tests for continuous variables and chi-square tests for categorical variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results

The study enrolled 120 children with severe thinness, evenly distributed between the Medical Nutrition Therapy (MNT) group and the Standard Nutrition Therapy (SNT) group. The demographic characteristics were comparable between the two groups at baseline, with an average age of 7.5 years and a gender distribution of approximately 52% male and 48% female.

Intervention Compliance: High compliance rates were observed in both groups, with 95% of the MNT group and 92% of the SNT group adhering to their prescribed nutritional interventions throughout the study period.

Nutritional and Health Outcomes: After the study in April 2017, significant improvements were observed in both groups. However, the MNT group demonstrated more pronounced enhancements in key indicators:

- **Body Mass Index (BMI):** The MNT group showed an average increase in BMI percentile from below the 5th percentile to the 15th percentile, whereas the SNT group improved from below the 5th percentile to the 10th percentile.
- **Height and Weight Gains:** Children in the MNT group exhibited greater increases in both height (average 3.2 cm vs. 2.5 cm in the SNT group) and weight (average 2.8 kg vs. 2.0 kg in the SNT group).
- **Nutritional Status:** Laboratory tests indicated significant improvements in markers of nutritional status (such as serum iron and vitamin levels) in the MNT group compared to the SNT group.
- **Health Improvements:** The MNT group reported fewer health complications such as infections and gastrointestinal disturbances compared to the SNT group during the study period.

The differences between the MNT and SNT groups were statistically significant, with p-values less than 0.05 for BMI, height and weight gains, and improvements in nutritional markers. This confirms the greater effectiveness of Medical Nutrition Therapy over Standard Nutrition Therapy in treating severe thinness among children. These results suggest that personalized Medical Nutrition Therapy offers a more effective approach to improving the nutritional and health outcomes in children with severe thinness compared to a standard approach.

Outcome Measures	MNT Group	SNT Group	P-Value
Initial BMI Percentile	Below 5th	Below 5th	N/A
Final BMI Percentile	15th	10th	<0.05
Height Gain (cm)	3.2	2.5	<0.05
Weight Gain (kg)	2.8	2.0	<0.05
Serum Iron Improvement	Significant	Moderate	<0.05
Vitamin Levels	Improved	Slight Improvement	<0.05
Health Complications	Fewer	More	<0.05

This table summarizes the key outcomes of the study, highlighting the effectiveness of MNT over SNT in various growth and health parameters among children aged 5 to 10 years with severe thinness.

Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate the superior efficacy of Medical Nutrition Therapy (MNT) over Standard Nutrition Therapy (SNT) in addressing severe thinness among children aged 5 to 10 years. The significant improvements observed in the MNT group across various parameters, including BMI percentile, height and weight gains, and improvements in serum iron and vitamin levels, underscore the value of personalized nutrition plans that cater to individual health needs and deficiencies [10,11].

The greater height and weight gains in the MNT group suggest that a tailored approach, which considers the specific nutritional and metabolic requirements of each child, is crucial for optimizing physical growth outcomes [12]. Moreover, the improvement in serum iron and vitamin levels highlights the role of targeted supplementation in correcting specific micronutrient deficiencies, which are often not adequately addressed by SNT. The reduction in health complications reported in the MNT group also indicates that a well-designed nutrition therapy can enhance immune function and overall health resilience, reducing the risk of infections and other health issues commonly associated with undernutrition [13,14].

These findings advocate for a shift in clinical practice towards more personalized nutrition interventions in pediatric populations, particularly for those at risk of or suffering from severe thinness [15,16]. Future studies should explore the long-term impacts of MNT and investigate its applicability in different socio-economic and cultural settings to broaden the understanding and implementation of this therapeutic approach. This research also calls for policymakers to consider the integration of medical nutrition services in standard pediatric care protocols to enhance the health outcomes of vulnerable populations [17-20].

Conclusion

The study conclusively demonstrated that Medical Nutrition Therapy (MNT) is more effective than Standard Nutrition Therapy (SNT) in improving the nutritional status and overall health of children aged 5 to 10 years with severe thinness. MNT, with its personalized dietary planning and specific nutrient supplementation, led to statistically significant improvements in BMI, height and weight gains, and serum nutrient levels compared to SNT. These results underscore the necessity of incorporating personalized nutritional assessments and interventions in pediatric healthcare protocols to address severe malnutrition effectively. This study encourages further exploration into the long-term benefits of MNT and its potential to be integrated into broader public health strategies aimed at combating pediatric undernutrition on a global scale.

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